

PLANNING WITH THE INTERACTIVE DISCIPLINE WHEEL

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WHAT IS EPISTEMIC INSIGHT?

Epistemic insight is defined as **'knowledge about knowledge'**.
But why does epistemic insight matter?

From students' early years at school, in England and many other countries, they engage with knowledge in compartmentalised subjects.

WEEKLY TIMETABLE				
MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY
REGISTRATION				
Maths	Maths	Science	English	English
BREAK				
Geography	English	Art	Maths	Maths
LUNCH				
History	Science	Sport	Art	History
English	R.E.	French	Art	History

Subjects are separated in time and space, often taught in different classrooms at different times of the day. One problem with this approach is that many questions people want to explore don't fit neatly into one box alone. This may seem obvious when we think about how questions work, but the way that lessons work mean that the need for joined-up thinking can be hidden from students. In school, questions come to students already sorted into their disciplines.

ep·i·ste·mic in·sight (ĕp'ĭ-stĕ'mĭk ĭn'sĭt')

Epistemic insight refers to 'knowledge about knowledge', and particularly knowledge about disciplines and how they interact.

Gaining epistemic insight is about developing an appreciation of the strengths and limitations of individual disciplines. One way to do this is to explore how two disciplines each investigate a cross-disciplinary question. Consider for example how science and history can each investigate 'Why did the Fire of London spread so quickly?'

BIG QUESTIONS

Today's Big Questions include 'Can a robot be a good companion?' 'Can and should genetic engineering be used to make better people?' 'Why do life and the universe exist?'

Big questions bridge science and the wider humanities and are frequently squeezed out of school education. That's because they don't fit neatly into one subject, they are often religiously sensitive and they call for teachers to explain how areas of knowledge interact.

WHY?

Big Questions are not currently covered in schools.

And yet these are questions about issues that affect the lives of individuals and society..They are also questions that we can explore through the lenses of many different disciplines

That's why we are developing tools and resources to help students to learn about the natures and interactions between disciplines.

SESSION 1

A HANDS-ON SCIENCE ENQUIRY

We recommend starting with a question that students can investigate first-hand through a hands-on science activity. The focus will be on learning about how science can help us to get to an answer, rather than the answer itself. There are lots of handy examples in science text books. Here's one that's fun to do:

“How many droplets of water can land on a coin before the water overflows?”

To investigate this question – scientifically - we can use a coin, a straw or pipette and a small container of water.

By “thinking like a scientist” – by making observations, predictions, testing, and comparing their results - students can build their understanding of science as a discipline. This is ‘epistemic knowledge’ – about science. Epistemic knowledge means knowledge about a discipline. Students gain or apply epistemic insight when they discover or use epistemic knowledge in practice.

Once we have asked and investigated a question through the lens of science and learnt how to ‘think like a scientist’, we can next to asking, investigating and thinking like a historian”?

Working around a selection of disciplines in the ‘Discipline Wheel’, students can learn and apply their epistemic knowledge through carefully chosen questions, one discipline at a time.

SPOTLIGHT ON SCIENCE

Science helps us to ask and explore questions about the natural world. The methods we use in science focus on making observations to test ideas and predictions. In science we say it's a good answer if many scientists have separately repeated the investigation and have reached the same conclusion.

How do clouds stay up?

Firstly we need to find out some things about water

Or a droplet of water caught in a leaf?

Have you seen a spider's web looking like this one?

What happens if two droplets run into each other?

Explore, Observe, Record

Dip a straw into a beaker of water and trap some water inside by putting a finger over the end.

Drop water droplets onto a penny. Draw or record your observations.

Why don't clouds fall out of the sky?

A cloud is made of tiny water droplets.

They are too light to be pulled to the ground.

The droplets of water join up – just as they did on the penny.

As it rains, the cloud shrinks.

Once the water is gone, there is no more cloud.

You may not see it shrinking because clouds are moving, blown along by the wind.

But you might see a rainbow!

What happens to the cloud after it rains?

Big droplets are pulled to the ground by gravity.

The sky darkens...

SESSION 2

A BRIDGING QUESTION

By exploring a cross-curricular or 'bridging question' students can build their epistemic knowledge about two disciplines – how they are similar, how they are different, and how they can work together.

SPOTLIGHT ON 'WHY DID THE TITANIC SINK?'

Science helps us to ask and explore **questions about the natural world**. The methods we use in science focus on making observations to test ideas and predictions. In science **we say it's a good answer** if many scientists have separately repeated the investigation and drew the same conclusion.

History helps us to ask and explore **questions about what happened in the past**. The **methods** we use in history focus on gathering testimonies, reports and artefacts to look at where people were, what they said, and what they wanted to do. Historians say **it's a good answer** if it is considered informative and credible – and justified in the context of other things known about the past.

WORKSHOP

Why did the spaghetti break?

Thinking Insightfully about how two different disciplines address the same question

In this 'hands-on' activity, students are investigating what happens as they put more and more weight into a gondola. They load pebbles into a gondola or basket which is hanging from a spaghetti bridge. We want to know – what is the force that breaks the spaghetti? But there's a twist. Explain to students that this activity is also a competition. Students work in groups of four. Each student puts a stone into the gondola. If they are the last person to put in a stone before the spaghetti breaks, they are the winner. But if they put in the stone that breaks the spaghetti, they lose! So – can they now use two different disciplines to investigate: Why did the spaghetti break?

WHAT'S GOING ON?

Students are investigating two things at the same time – the behaviour of the people and the behaviour of the spaghetti. Ask them – which discipline can best help us to measure and explain the force that breaks the spaghetti?

Which discipline asks questions about the behaviour of the people and helps us to think about the tactics they use and how competitively they play the game? Do they agree that working with both disciplines together can give us a richer understanding of why the spaghetti breaks?

Why did the spaghetti break?

THINKING LIKE A PHYSICIST

This is an opportunity to see that physics can help us to investigate a carefully framed question about the natural world. We are discovering the properties and behaviour of a physical object – a piece of spaghetti – acting as a bridge. When we think like a physicist and ask, “Why does the spaghetti break?” we mean: ‘what is the force that breaks the spaghetti?’ To carry out an investigation we could gather observations and measurements while systematically increasing the weight on the bridge.

Weight in g	Distance from top to bottom of bridge in cm
10g	
20g	
30g	

LAYERS OF EXPLANATION

When we bring the disciplines together they give us different layers of explanation. It’s as though there is a layer of explanation that is about why people do what they do – which deserves attention before we discuss the physics. Without the people playing the game, we wouldn’t have the spaghetti bridge at all.

This activity can also help us to appreciate why the questions that physics asks can often lead to answers that are well supported by evidence and that get widespread agreement. In contrast, if we ask a Big Question we are less likely to arrive at a simple agreed-upon answer. We can also choose to zoom in and just consider the physics – after all, whatever the people are doing, there is a force that breaks the bridge.

THINKING LIKE A SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGIST

But in this scenario, there is also a bigger question to explore which is to do with the social world of people and how they behave. The people playing the game are each unique and each time they play, the story will unfold differently. As psychologists we can interview the players to try to find out what they were each thinking at the time.

WAYS OF KNOWING AND HOW THEY INTERACT

If we think about how these lessons help us to understand our world, we can see that when science investigates carefully framed questions about the natural world, it does not replace the need or role of other ways of knowing like history, theology and psychology. But at the same time, science informs our thinking and that means better answers in the end.

SESSION 3

A REAL-WORLD OPPORTUNITY OR PROBLEM

Working on a real-world opportunity or problem gives students insight into how disciplines can work together to create better solutions.

Students can be put into groups that each work with a particular discipline. Groups of students can come together to offer their different disciplinary perspectives on the opportunity or problem.

Exploring the question: 'Can Water Flow Uphill?' through multiple lenses

How can we use technology to move water uphill?

Are there places in the world where we can see water moving uphill?

How can perspective in art be used to create the appearance of water flowing uphill?

Some materials can soak up water - but how high can it go?

When water evaporates it moves upwards. Is it still water while it is in this state?

Water moves uphill in plants and trees because of capillary action. Capillaries are narrow tubes and spaces in many natural and artificial materials.

EPISTEMIC INSIGHT INTERACTIVE DISCIPLINE WHEEL ONLINE

CONSTRUCT A QUESTION TO ASK

"Will we ever live and work in space?"

CHOOSE DISCIPLINES TO ADDRESS YOUR QUESTION

Selected Disciplines: astronomy, theology, chemistry, marketing

AI OUTPUTS: Sure, here are my thoughts on the question "Will we ever live and work in space?" from the lenses of astronomy, theology, chemistry, and marketing:

ASTRONOMY

QUESTIONS: What are the physical challenges of living and working in space? How can we protect ourselves from the harsh environment of space? How can we provide for our basic needs, such as food, water, and air?

METHODS: Astronomers use a variety of methods to study space, including telescopes, satellites, and probes. They also use computer models to simulate the conditions of space.

NORMS OF THOUGHT: Astronomers value evidence-based reasoning and objectivity. They also value peer review, which is the process of having other scientists review their work before it is published.

THEOLOGY

QUESTIONS: What does it mean to be human in the context of space? What are the ethical implications of living and working in space? How can we ensure that space exploration is used for good?

METHODS: Theologians use a variety of methods to study these questions, including scripture, tradition, and reason. They also engage in dialogue with other disciplines, such as science and philosophy.

NORMS OF THOUGHT: Theologians value critical thinking and open-mindedness. They also value the importance of faith and spirituality.

CHEMISTRY

QUESTIONS: How can we develop new materials that are suitable for use in space? How can we produce food and water in space? How can we protect ourselves from the radiation in space?

METHODS: Chemists use a variety of methods to study these questions, including experimentation, modeling, and simulation. They also collaborate with engineers and other scientists to develop new technologies.

NORMS OF THOUGHT: Chemists value evidence-based reasoning and reproducibility. They also value the importance of peer review.

MARKETING

QUESTIONS: How can we make space exploration more appealing to the public? How can we raise the necessary funds to support space exploration? How can we ensure that the benefits of space exploration are shared by everyone?

METHODS: Marketers use a variety of methods to study these questions, including surveys, focus groups, and social media analytics. They also collaborate with other disciplines, such as economics and psychology.

NORMS OF THOUGHT: Marketers value data-driven decision-making and creativity. They also value the importance of understanding the needs of their target audience.

In conclusion, there are many challenges to living and working in space. However, the advances in science and technology are making it increasingly possible. The four disciplines discussed above each have a unique perspective to offer on this question. By working together, we can overcome the challenges and make space exploration a reality for future generations.

Here are some additional thoughts on the norms of thought for each discipline:

ASTRONOMY: The norm of evidence-based reasoning is particularly important in astronomy, as the discipline is based on the observation of the physical world. Astronomers must be able to critically evaluate the evidence and draw sound conclusions.

THEOLOGY: The norm of critical thinking is important in theology, as it allows theologians to examine their beliefs and assumptions critically. This is important in order to avoid bias and to arrive at a more accurate understanding of the world.

CHEMISTRY: The norm of reproducibility is important in chemistry, as it ensures that the results of experiments can be replicated by others. This is important in order to build trust in the discipline and to avoid errors.

MARKETING: The norm of understanding the needs of the target audience is important in marketing, as it ensures that the messages and products are designed to appeal to the people who are most likely to be interested in them. This is important in order to be successful in the marketplace.

THE EI DISCIPLINE WHEEL IS IN TEACHERS' MODE

EI DISCIPLINE WHEEL FOR TEACHERS

Teachers Students 8-10 11-12 13-15 16+

You can use the Discipline Wheel to get suggestions for how your students can investigate a question – through the lenses of different subject disciplines. Write a Question in the Question box below.

Why is water clear?

Click the disciplines you want by clicking them in the Discipline Wheel. If you don't see a discipline you're looking for, click 'edit mode' to change one or more disciplines in the Wheel. Then click on them.

Edit Mode

OUTPUT BY EI DISCIPLINE WHEEL:

The Epistemic Insight Framework is a way of learning about different disciplines by exploring relevant questions, methods, and answers. It helps students build epistemic insight into what makes each discipline unique, how it relates to other disciplines, and how to determine a good answer. Let's explore how this framework can be applied to investigating the question, "Why is water clear?" in various disciplines:

1. Natural Sciences:

Relevant question: What properties of water make it transparent?

Methods in this discipline could involve experimenting with water using different filters or observing how different substances dissolve in water. Students could also research and learn about the molecular structure of water and how it affects its transparency.

Epistemic insight: This investigation helps students understand the scientific principles behind water's clarity, such as its molecular arrangement and how it interacts with light. They learn to distinguish the properties of water that make it transparent from those that do not.

2. Theology:

Relevant question: How does water's clarity relate to religious beliefs?

Methods in this discipline may include discussing religious texts, stories, and symbols that involve water. Students could explore religious ceremonies or rituals involving water and reflect on the symbolic meanings associated with clarity and purity.

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Epistemic insight: Through this exploration, students understand the role of water as a symbol in various religious traditions. They recognize how water's clarity can represent spiritual purity or reveal deeper meanings in religious practices.

3. English Literature:

Relevant question: How is water's clarity depicted in literature?

Methods in this discipline may involve reading and analyzing literary works that feature water imagery. Students could explore descriptive language, metaphors, and symbols related to water's clarity in poems, stories, or novels.

Epistemic insight: By exploring literature, students develop an understanding of how authors use water's transparency to convey emotions, themes, or character traits. They recognize that water's clarity can be used as a literary device to enhance storytelling.

4. Creative Arts:

Relevant question: How can we visually represent water's clarity?

Methods in this discipline may involve creating paintings, drawings, or sculptures that depict water's transparency. Students could also experiment with different artistic techniques such as shading, blending, or using transparent materials to represent the clear nature of water.

Epistemic insight: Through their artistic exploration, students understand how to visually represent water's transparency, exploring techniques and materials that mimic its clarity. They also recognize that art can be a powerful means of expression and communication across disciplines.

5. Geography:

Relevant question: How does water's clarity vary in different bodies of water?

Methods in this discipline may involve studying and comparing water sources like rivers, lakes, and oceans. Students could conduct experiments or tests to measure water clarity, develop maps depicting water clarity in different regions, or explore the impact of human activities on water transparency.

Epistemic insight: By investigating water clarity in different geographical contexts, students develop a spatial understanding of how various factors, such as pollution, sedimentation, or natural conditions, can influence water's clarity. They discover how geography intersects with scientific concepts.

Note: It is important to adapt the complexity and scope of each investigation to suit the age and abilities of the 8-year-old students.

QUESTION: WHAT CRITERIA CAN TELL US IF AN AI IS A FRIEND?

EI DISCIPLINE WHEEL

Teachers / Students | 8-10 | 11-12 | 13-15 | 16+

You can use the Discipline Wheel to get suggestions for how your students can investigate a question - through the lenses of different subject disciplines. Write a Question in the Question box below.

What criteria can tell us if an AI is a friend?

Click the disciplines you want by clicking them in the Discipline Wheel. If you don't see a discipline you're looking for, click 'edit mode' to change one or more disciplines in the Wheel. Then click on them.

Press submit and wait for the program to respond. And watch out, the AI doesn't have a teacher's sense and the suggestions it puts together can miss essential information such as to check for allergies.

Submit

Canterbury Christ Church University

Engineering and Computing:

- Preferred questions: How can we design an AI system that promotes friendly behavior and ethical decision-making? What technical criteria can be used to determine whether an AI is a friend?
- Methods: Experimentation, algorithm design, machine learning, data analysis.
- Good answer in this discipline: A good answer would provide a set of technical specifications or design principles that an AI system should meet to be considered a friend. It should also explain the potential risks and limitations associated with evaluating an AI's "friendliness" purely based on technical criteria.

Theology:

- Preferred questions: What does it mean for an AI to be a friend in a theological context? Can an AI possess genuine love or compassion?
- Methods: Religious scripture interpretation, philosophical analysis, ethical reflection.
- Good answer in this discipline: A good answer would explore theological concepts such as love, free will, and the nature of personhood to determine whether an AI can be considered a friend. It would address the moral and theological implications of relying on AI for friendship and discuss potential ethical concerns.

Law:

- Preferred questions: What legal rights and responsibilities should be assigned to AI as "friends"? How can AI be held accountable for their actions?
- Methods: Legal analysis, case studies, policy evaluation.
- Good answer in this discipline: A good answer would consider the legal framework

surrounding AI, including issues of liability, privacy, and consent. It would propose legal guidelines and regulations to define the criteria for an AI to be considered a friend and discuss the potential legal consequences of AI's actions.

English Literature:

- Preferred questions: How is the concept of friendship explored in literature and can AI fit into that framework? What literary tropes or motifs can be used to represent friendship with AI?
- Methods: Literary analysis, close reading, interpretation of literary texts.
- Good answer in this discipline: A good answer would examine literary works that address the theme of friendship and explore how AI can be portrayed as a friend in literature. It would provide examples of literary devices used to represent AI friendships and discuss the implications of these representations.

Psychology:

- Preferred questions: How do humans perceive and form friendships? Can AI exhibit behaviors that humans perceive as friendly? How can psychological criteria be used to evaluate an AI's friendliness?
- Methods: Psychological studies, experimentation, surveys, data analysis.
- Good answer in this discipline: A good answer would delve into the psychological aspects of friendship and examine whether AI can meet the criteria that humans use to perceive and form friendships. It would discuss research findings on human-AI interactions and outline psychological tests or models that can measure an AI's friendliness.

Epistemic Insight

EI DISCIPLINE WHEEL FOR TEACHERS

Teachers Students 8-10 11-12 13-15 16+

You can use the Discipline Wheel to see how scholars in different disciplines would investigate your Big Question. Write a Question in the Question box below.

What criteria can tell us if an AI is a friend?

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The Epistemic Insight Framework is a way of learning about different disciplines by exploring relevant questions, methods, and answers. It helps students build epistemic insight into what makes a discipline distinctive and how it is similar to other disciplines. By investigating the question, "What criteria can tell us if an AI is a friend?" through different lenses, you can help your 14-year-old students gain a deeper understanding of various subjects. Here's how you can approach each discipline in the classroom:

Edit Mode

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1. Engineering and Computing:

Question: What technical features can AI possess to simulate friendship?

Methods: Students can research and analyze the programming and technical aspects of AI systems. They can create a basic chatbot or an AI algorithm and identify features that can simulate friendship, such as natural language processing, emotional recognition, or personalized responses.

Good Answer: A good answer in this discipline could identify the specific technical components responsible for simulating friendship in an AI system, explaining how these features contribute to human-like interactions.

2. Theology:

Question: How does the concept of friendship align with the divine nature?

Methods: Students can explore religious texts and teachings to understand the spiritual significance of friendship. They can analyze how religious figures or texts define and emphasize friendship, and compare it to AI's ability to exhibit similar qualities.

Good Answer: Students would be expected to provide insights into how the concept of friendship is portrayed in different religious contexts and whether an AI's ability to be a friend aligns with those beliefs.

3. Languages:

Question: How do different languages and cultures define and express friendship?

Methods: Students can research friendship-related terms and expressions in various languages. They can explore how different cultures perceive and value friendship, comparing it to an AI's understanding of friendship.

Good Answer: A good answer would involve examining different cultural perspectives on friendship, exploring how specific words and phrases capture the essence of friendship in different languages, and comparing it to an AI's capacity to comprehend those elements.

4. English Literature:

Question: How do literary works explore the themes of friendship, and can AI replicate those experiences?

Methods: Students can read literary works that emphasize the themes of friendship, whether it's novels, plays, or poems. They can analyze the interactions and dynamics between characters, discussing whether an AI can genuinely replicate those experiences.

Good Answer: Students should demonstrate their understanding of how literature portrays friendship and critically evaluate whether AI can replicate the depth, complexity, and emotional connection found in literary friendships.

5. History:

Question: How have societal perceptions and expectations of friendship evolved over time?

Methods: Students can research how friendship was valued in different historical periods and cultures. They can examine primary and secondary sources, literature, art, and personal accounts to track changes in societal perceptions of friendship and discuss whether an AI can fit within those historical contexts.

Good Answer: A good answer would involve showing an understanding of how friendship norms have changed over time and explaining whether AI can adapt to or replicate the expectations of friendship present in different historical periods.

6. Psychology:

Question: What psychological traits and behaviors are typically associated with friendship, and can AI exhibit them?

Methods: Students can study the psychological research on friendship, including empathy, trust, support, and companionship. They can explore how AI can simulate these traits and compare it to human friendships.

Good Answer: Students should demonstrate an understanding of the psychology behind friendship and evaluate AI's ability to exhibit key traits associated with genuine friendships based on psychological research.

By approaching the question from various disciplines, students can gain epistemic insight into the unique perspectives and methods used in each field. They will learn to analyze complex problems from different angles, recognizing the similarities and differences between disciplines. A good answer in each discipline would reflect a thoughtful understanding of the specific discipline's criteria, concepts, and perspectives while presenting a logical and supported argument or analysis. Remember, encourage critical thinking and fostering discussions among students as they analyze and compare their findings across disciplines.

THE EPISTEMIC INSIGHT CURRICULUM FRAMEWORK

The nature of science in real world contexts and multidisciplinary arenas

Scientism is not a necessary presupposition of science.

Science informs our thinking about every aspect of our lives.
Some questions are more amenable to science than others.
There are some questions that science hasn't yet and may never be able to answer.

Science begins with observations of the natural world and constructing ways to explain our observations.
Science informs our thinking about Big Questions.

Some questions are more metaphysically sensitive than others.

A school or university is a multidisciplinary arena.
Different disciplines have different preferred questions, methods and norms of thought.

Science has some similarities and some differences with other ways of knowing.

Ways of knowing and how they interact

Big Questions that bridge science, religion and the wider humanities seldom have simple agreed-upon answers.
Science and religion are not necessarily incompatible.

Today we ask Big Questions like: 'Why does the universe exist?' and 'Can a robot be a friend?'
Some people say that science and religion are compatible and some people say they are not.

Relationships between science and religion

Science and religion are mostly concerned with different types of questions, including different types of why question.

■ ADVANCED
■ INTERMEDIATE
■ STARTER

ASSESSMENT - WAYS TO EVIDENCE EPISTEMIC INSIGHT

EI DISCIPLINE WHEEL FOR TEACHERS

Teachers Students 8-10 11-12 13-15 16+

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How do we make driverless cars Safer?

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Edit Mode

Press submit and wait for the program to respond. And watch out, the AI doesn't have a teacher's sense and the suggestions it puts together can miss essential information such as to check for allergies.

This is a demonstration version of the interface. There are examples of it working on the webpage.

Submit

Here are some examples of statements that indicate students are gaining epistemic insight.

I am building my epistemic insight when I have a chance to observe in a science lesson how real things work naturally, where the investigation isn't the type that needs to be engineered or manipulated by a teacher to work 'successfully'.

I am building my epistemic insight by becoming familiar with key terms and ideas such as disciplines, amenable to science, preferred questions and methods and norms of thought, metaphysical sensitivity (metaphysical reductionism and methodological reductionism)

I am sharing my understanding of epistemic insight when I explain the issue of entrenched compartmentalisation to other people and the gaps it can mean exist in some students' appreciation of the power, relevance and limitations of different disciplines.

I am building awareness of epistemic insight when I ask and explore Big Questions that are about human personhood and the nature of reality and explain that they bridge science and religion and can also be explored through many more ways of knowing.

LEARNING REVIEW

I am confident 😊 I'd like further support 😐 I don't understand ☹️

I am being epistemically insightful when:

- I can sort small questions that can be answered by science from bigger questions that require one or more other disciplines 😊 😐 ☹️
- I can explain how science and theology help me to investigate a Big question about the nature of human personhood..... 😊 😐 ☹️
- I understand that some questions are more amenable to science than others 😊 😐 ☹️
- I can explain that science and theology have different methods and norms of thought 😊 😐 ☹️

LEARNING REVIEW

I am confident 😊 I'd like further support 😐 I don't understand ☹️

I am being epistemically insightful when:

- I can sort questions in to different disciplines..... 😊 😐 ☹️
- I can explain that some different disciplines use similar methods to answer their preferred questions 😊 😐 ☹️
- I understand that some questions are more amenable to science than others. 😊 😐 ☹️
- I can explain that disciplines have preferred methods, questions and norms of thought (values)..... 😊 😐 ☹️

LEARNING REVIEW

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THE EPISTEMIC INSIGHT INITIATIVE GLOSSARY

Big Questions

Big Questions are complex and invite enquiry through many disciplines. They seldom have simple agreed-upon answers.

'Big Questions about human personhood and the nature of reality' are questions that stretch across discipline boundaries and across subject boundaries in schools. They are also questions on which both science and religion have something to say.

Examples are: 'Why do life and the universe exist?' 'Are humans significant in the universe?' 'Can a robot be a friend?' 'Why does water matter in our lives?' 'Are you what you eat?'

Real-world opportunities and problems

Real-world opportunities and problems are practical issues to work with that you can connect to key themes such as citizenship, health and wellbeing and sustainability. For example:

Where should we put a wind turbine? How do we stay safe during a pandemic? Can computers make some decisions for us?

Disciplines

A discipline is an approach to enquiry and a branch or field of knowledge. There are examples of subjects that match the name of a discipline such as: Science, history, geography, and mathematics.

Subjects

A school subject may focus on working with one discipline or it may cover more than one.

Discipline Wheel

A tool which has a space for a question in the centre of a wheel of disciplines.

If the question is a Big Question like 'what does it mean to be alive?' then students could be invited to think critically about how each of the disciplines around the wheel could help them to investigate the question.

Or if the question is a more focused question, students could be asked to consider which of the disciplines would be particularly important to work with.

Epistemic Insight

Knowledge about knowledge, particularly knowledge about disciplines and how they interact.

Bridging question

A question that is chosen or designed by the teacher to bridge two disciplines. An example is "Why did the Titanic sink?" which bridges science and history. A bridging question means that students can compare and contrast how two disciplines interpret and investigate the question.

Bridging questions can be used by specialist teachers in secondary schools to show how their discipline connects to another discipline taught in school.

Science questions

Science addresses questions about the natural world. Good questions for science are questions that we can investigate by gathering observations to build and test ideas. For older students we explain that scientists use many methods in their work. The scientific method involves designing investigations that generate observations which we can use to test a hypothesis.

A good answer in science helps us to understand how the natural world works and is supported by repeatable observations and measurements.

Observation

Science begins with observations. When we observe in science we are making connections between our theories and what we observe.

The Natural world

Questions about the natural world deal with the building blocks of nature such as fire, water, land, air, minerals, plants and all living things. Science investigates and helps us to understand how the natural world works.

Bubble tool

We can use this tool to decide and talk about how scientific a question is.

Here is a question that is a good one for science: 'How does the size of a parachute affect how quickly an object falls to earth?'

CHARACTERISING DISCIPLINES

Here are some more summaries of disciplines – in terms of their preferred questions, methods and norms of thought. They can be adapted for different age groups.

Science

Science helps us to ask and explore questions about the natural world. The methods we use in science focus on making observations to test ideas and predictions. In science we say it's a good answer if many scientists have separately repeated the investigation and drew the same conclusion.

Geography

Geography helps us to ask and explore questions about people and places. The methods we use in geography focus on gathering observations and other kinds of data to look at where people live and how landscapes change. Geographers say it's a good answer if there are many different types of evidence to support it and if the evidence is not unfairly stacked to suit one group or another.

History

History studies the past and changing accounts of the past. History asks questions and teaches us about things that happened in the past (sometimes referred to as the 'stuff' of history), as well as the way history is understood. This includes questions about causes and consequences, change and continuity, similarity and difference, significance, and interpretations. It's a good answer if it tells us something new about a previously unknown even in the past, or provides new evidence for why something in the past occurred.

Engineering

Engineering helps us to ask and explore questions about how technology can improve people's lives. The methods we use in engineering focus on testing the designs of technologies to assess how well these meet their criteria. Engineers say it's a good answer if it explains how to create technologies that are safe, ethical and reliable.

The Arts

The Arts help us to ask and explore questions about how to express and communicate what is in our imaginations through forms that we can share. The methods we use in the arts focus on discussing the medium, tools and techniques used, and how meanings in art are perceived by artists and audiences. Artists, audiences, and art critics bring in their own views of the world to say whether a work of art or approach is a good answer.

Religious studies

Religious studies help us to ask and explore questions about religious faith, practices and experiences. The methods we use focus on gathering sources, texts and stories that express beliefs about human existence and purpose. Scholars in this field say it's a good answer if it is considered informative about a system, history and experience of belief – and justified in the context of other things known about a religious tradition.

Philosophy

Philosophy asks fundamental questions about existence, reason, knowledge, values and language. The methods we use in philosophy are based on rational inquiry, systematic thought and critical reflection. One branch of philosophy is known as epistemology. Epistemology is the branch of philosophy that studies knowledge. Another branch of philosophy is Logic which emphasises the study of reasoning and argument. It's a good answer if, given certain premises, certain conclusions are unavoidably implied.

Economics

Economics is a discipline that studies of how people use resources and respond to incentives, it is also the study of decision-making. It often involves topics like wealth and finance. Economics asks a wide range of questions like: Why are some countries rich and some countries poor? What causes recessions? How do people respond to an increase in prices? The methods used in economics involve forecasting models using quantitative analysis, as well as historical analysis. It's a good answer if it tells us something about how people make financial decisions.

Psychology

Psychology is the scientific study of mind and behaviour. Psychology includes the study of conscious and unconscious phenomena, including feelings and thoughts. As a discipline psychology involves aspects of both the natural and social sciences. There are different types of psychology like behavioural, social, cognitive, and psychoanalytic. Although each of these types will have different questions, most of the questions relate to behaviour of individuals or groups. Some psychologists use empirical methods, while others use more theoretical methods. It's a good answer if it tells us something about why people behave in particular ways.

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